

Original Article

Possibilities and Challenges for ESDP's Trainees to Launch a Business: with special reference to Dharwad district

Dr. Shweta Maruti Hulkunda

Assistant professor, M.P.Mirji College of Commerce
Beluguam, Karnataka

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Abstract:

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The study examined the Possibilities and Challenges for ESDP Trainees to Launch a Business in the Dharwad district. It is descriptive research. 500 samples were examined, and a systematic random sampling procedure was used to choose the samples. The data is analysed using SPSS Ver. 20. The data are presented using frequency, Paired t-test, and ANOVA tests. The primary data was collected through questionnaires from the beneficiaries of ESDP's.

The study shows that the training facilities like EAP and E-SDP programmes are very necessary to boost self-employment and it is fruitful evidence to know how changes found in trainees. Entrepreneurship and skill-development initiatives can have a big impact on a country's GDP, manufacturing output, service sector, employment growth, and exports. After the training only beneficiaries come to know their weaknesses and strengths and they help in promoting to establish an enterprise. Here researcher conclude the topic that the trainings like ESDP are very important to motivate in establishing own businesses.

Keywords: ESDP, EAP, Challenges, Possibilities, MSMEs.

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Introduction

A task of entrepreneurship is taking risks. Many businesses owners battle with various problems that are connected to their companies. The importance of entrepreneurship to the expansion of the economy is well accepted. The Indian government has made every effort to address the difficulties, but they still exist in some sectors, particularly those that employ low-skilled, uneducated, and rural businesses. In this paper, the researcher looked at the challenges and opportunities that face entrepreneurs in the Dharwad district of Karnataka state. The study takes into account the information learned by EAP and E-SDP, the application of PMEGP to ESDP trainees, the shortcomings they find in them after the training, the need for post-training assistance.

Objectives

1. To examine the knowledge and weakness found by the ESDP beneficiaries after the training.
2. To evaluate the needs of after training assistance to the beneficiaries of ESDP.

Research methodology

In the Dharwad district, the study looked at the Opportunities and Difficulties for ESDP Trainees to Start a business. It is descriptive research. 500 samples are collected from every taluka in the Dharwad District for the study. The study uses systematic sampling since there is a list of the population that is both easily accessible and rather lengthy. Since a sample size of 4% is needed, the fifth item is randomly chosen from the first 25 samples, and every subsequent 25 samples are then automatically chosen. The data is analysed using SPSS Ver. 20. The hypotheses were tested using the ANOVA test.

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Address for correspondence:

Shweta Maruti Hulkunda, Assistant professor, M.P.Mirji College of Commerce, Beluguam, Karnataka

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Data presentation and results

Table 1.1 breaks down the knowledge gained by EAP beneficiaries by gender and the type of business established. In the manufacturing sector, 43.08 percent of men had the most expertise in terms of project selection and project profile creation. 19.17% of men and women, respectively, believed that marketing efforts helped the manufacturing and service sectors the most. Pricing of goods or services was dealt with by the manufacturing industry, which had a 32.81 percent female workforce. Those who have never formed a business and have a male to female ratio of 23.70 are more receptive to export opportunities. 38.66% of males responded when asked about the manufacturing industry's infrastructure. Questions from non-business owners about financial institutions, working capital, accounting, and product costing had a 34.56 percent male response rate.

Table 1.1 Knowledge gained by the beneficiaries of Entrepreneurship Awareness Programme

Particulars	Manufacturing		Service		No business started		Total
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Product or project selection and project profile preparation	109 (43.08)	41 (16.20)	20 (7.90)	36 (14.22)	04 (1.58)	43 (17.02)	253 (100)
Marketing avenues / techniques	35 (11.98)	56 (19.17)	56 (19.17)	25 (8.56)	71 (24.31)	49 (16.81)	292 (100)
Product / service pricing	76 (29.68)	84 (32.81)	48 (18.75)	28 (10.93)	14 (5.46)	06 (2.37)	256 (100)
Export opportunities	20 (8.62)	35 (15.08)	48 (20.68)	24 (10.34)	55 (23.70)	50 (21.58)	232 (100)
Infrastructural facilities available	31 (11.52)	65 (24.16)	104 (38.66)	54 (20.07)	10 (3.71)	05 (1.88)	269 (100)
Financial institutions, cash flow, accounting, product costing	88 (31.65)	14 (5.03)	36 (12.94)	27 (9.71)	17 (6.11)	96 (34.56)	278 (100)

Source: Primary Survey

Table 1.2 breaks down the knowledge that E-SDP beneficiaries have acquired by gender and business type. Males who had not yet started a business had the lowest response rate, while females working in the service sector had the highest response rate (22.52 percent). Among the 394 respondents that selected their sectors, 27.66% of the female respondents from the service sector did so favourably. Finance and marketing received favourable responses from the service industry girls, who scored an average of 29.43 and 32.91 percent of working women in the service sector expressed approval for the creation of project reports. The average number of industrial visits made by female employees in the service industry is 28.10. Service industry female employees performed well on various registration processes, scoring an average of 32.74. The aforementioned statistics make it clear that women who worked in the service sector benefited the most from E-SDP.

Table 1.2 Knowledge gained by the beneficiaries of Entrepreneurship-cum-Skill Development Programme

Particulars	Manufacturing		Service		No business started		Total
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Market Survey	50 (13.40)	71 (19.03)	80 (21.44)	84 (22.52)	30 (8.04)	58 (15.54)	373 (100)
Selection of Industry	87 (22.08)	34 (8.62)	62 (15.73)	109 (27.66)	13 (3.29)	89 (22.62)	394 (100)
Finance and Marketing	62 (19.62)	44 (13.92)	32 (10.12)	93 (29.43)	53 (16.77)	32 (10.14)	316 (100)
Preparation of Project Report	90 (28.21)	13 (4.07)	23 (7.21)	105 (32.91)	16 (5.01)	73 (22.59)	319 (100)
Industrial Visit	61 (18.04)	53 (15.68)	50 (14.79)	95 (28.10)	35 (10.35)	44 (13.04)	338 (100)
Process of various registration	85 (24.85)	37 (10.81)	30 (8.77)	112 (32.74)	31 (9.06)	47 (13.77)	342 (100)

Source: Primary Survey

Beneficiaries of the Entrepreneurship Awareness Program acknowledged their deficiencies after the training, which are depicted in table 1. 3. When asked about their level of confidence, 215 people responded, the majority of whom were women employed in the service industry, with an average response of 26.97. Of those who firmly identify

as uninformed, 24.81 percent of men work in manufacturing. Women, who make up 29.08 percent of the population and work in the service industry, typically report feeling unmotivated. Women working in the service sector, on average, significantly identify with traditional ideas (25.84%). 30% of the 120 respondents who said there was a low percentage of smart work were female and from the service sector.

Table 1.3 Weakness found by beneficiaries of Entrepreneurship Awareness Programme after attending the training

Particulars	Manufacturing		Service		No business started		Total
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Low confidence	56 (26.04)	40 (18.60)	26 (12.09)	58 (26.97)	31 (14.41)	04 (1.89)	215 (100)
Lack of knowledge	43 (15.92)	67 (24.81)	63 (23.33)	52 (19.25)	40 (14.81)	05 (1.88)	270 (100)
Lack of motivation	70 (27.88)	34 (13.54)	25 (9.96)	73 (29.08)	42 (16.73)	07 (2.81)	251 (100)
Traditional believes	96 (35.95)	29 (10.86)	36 (13.48)	69 (25.84)	14 (5.24)	23 (8.63)	267 (100)
Low rate of smart work	21 (17.5)	18 (15)	19 (15.83)	36 (30)	20 (16.66)	06 (5.01)	120 (100)

Source: Primary Survey

According to the type of business and gender, Table 1.4 shows the participants in the Entrepreneurship-cum-Skill Development Program's areas of weakness. There are four programme flaws that have been found. lack of financial assistance Among the 312 respondents that responded, 31.73 percent came from the service industry. Female respondents made up 34.48% of those who provided extremely high ratings for having sufficient skills. 29.36% of respondents who strongly agreed that marketing awareness was important were female. Among those who identified the sophisticated packaging, 36.6 percent were men working for companies in the manufacturing sector. The data clearly shows that the majority of respondents were women who were employed in the service sector.

Table 1.4 Weakness found by the beneficiaries of Entrepreneurship-cum-Skill Development Programme

Particulars	Manufacturing		Service		No business started		Total
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Lack of financial assistance	93 (29.80)	06 (1.92)	23 (7.37)	99 (31.73)	13 (4.16)	78 (25.02)	312 (100)
Adequate skills	102 (25.12)	35 (8.62)	30 (7.38)	140 (34.48)	05 (1.23)	94 (23.17)	406 (100)
Marketing awareness	28 (7.40)	111 (29.36)	93 (24.60)	62 (16.40)	41 (10.84)	43 (11.4)	378 (100)
Advance packaging	123 (36.60)	09 (2.67)	20 (5.95)	107 (31.84)	10 (2.97)	67 (20.27)	336 (100)

Source: Primary Survey

Table 1.5 breaks down the needs for post-training assistance based on the type of business & gender. In the study, four different types of post-training assistance were discovered. The financial assistance was well received by females who had not yet launched a business. The girls in the service sector gave the problem-solving cell enthusiastic responses, scoring an average of 28.18. A separate cell was required for every issue by 32.96 percent of women working in the service sector, compared to males in the manufacturing sector, who scored an average of 27.60.

Table 1.5 Needs of after training assistance bifurcated on the basis of nature of business and gender

Particulars	Manufacturing		Service		No business started		Total
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Assistance for Loan	23 (13.21)	24 (13.79)	32 (18.39)	33 (18.96)	11 (6.32)	51 (29.33)	174 (100)
Problem solving cell	35 (23.48)	14 (9.39)	16 (10.73)	42 (28.18)	16 (10.73)	26 (17.49)	149 (100)
Assistance for Marketing	45 (27.60)	12 (7.36)	26 (15.95)	39 (23.92)	01 (0.61)	40 (24.56)	163 (100)
Separate Cell to solve all the problem	06 (2.19)	68 (24.90)	20 (7.32)	90 (32.96)	82 (30.03)	07 (2.6)	273 (100)

Source: Primary Survey

Hypotheses testing

H0: The recipients' level of knowledge is relatively low after EAP training.

H0: The recipients' level of knowledge is relatively low after E-SDP training.

H0: There is no significant difference between the needs of after training assistance.

Table 1.6 Annova

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between groups	4343.556	5	868.7111	1.099919	0.38	2.5
Within groups	23694	30	789.8			
Total	28037.56	35				

Source: Primary Survey

Table 1.7 Annova

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between groups	18874.47	5	3774.894	11.8	2.12	2.53
Within groups	9519.833	30	317.3278			
Total	28394.31	35				

Source: Primary Survey

Table 1.8 Annova

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between groups	1929.875	5	385.975	0.6	0.6	2.7
Within groups	10279.75	18	571.0972			
Total	12209.63	23				

Source: Primary Survey

Tables 1.6 to 1.8 display the interpretation based on p-values and their accompanying potentiality. The following test results are used to determine if a null hypothesis should be accepted:

The coefficient is not highly significant based on the F-value of 1.099919 and level of significance of 0.38 since 0.38 is not less than 0.05 level of significance. We are unable to rule out the null hypothesis based on the results. After receiving EAP training, the researcher discovers that the recipient's degree of knowledge is relatively high.

The degree of significance indicates that there is more than 0.05, i.e., 2.12. Between groups, the mean square value is 3774.894, whereas within groups, it is 317.3278. Because 2.12 is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the coefficient is not highly significant. We are unable to rule out the null hypothesis based on the results. After receiving E-SDP training, the researcher discovers that the recipient's level of knowledge is relatively high.

It is evident that the level of significance is more than 0.05, i.e., 0.6. Between groups, the mean square value is 385.975, whereas within groups, it is 571.0972. Because 0.6 does not fall below the 0.05 level of significance, the coefficient is not highly significant. We are unable to rule out the null hypothesis based on the results. Researchers discover a sizable variation in the needs for help following training.

Conclusion

The main objectives of entrepreneurship and skill development programmes are to motivate young people to pursue entrepreneurship as a profession and to provide them with the skills necessary to successfully identify and seize work and self-employment possibilities. Everyone is aware of how critical skill development and entrepreneurship are to the expansion of the Indian economy. Entrepreneurship and skill-development initiatives can have a big impact on a country's GDP, manufacturing output, service sector, employment growth, and exports.

The study shows that the training facilities like EAP and E-SDP programmes are very necessary to boost self-employment and it is fruitful evidence to know how changes found in trainees. After the training only beneficiaries come to know their weaknesses and strengths and they help in promoting to establish an enterprise. Here researcher conclude the topic that the trainings like ESDP are very important to motivate in establishing own businesses.

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